

Implementing actions to promote wellbeing in Italian academics. Insights, challenges and drivers from a national survey

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Purpose

This study is part of the work being developed by the QoL@Work network, which is an Italian academic network focused on the quality of working life in academia. One of the network's objectives is to share good practices for assessing and managing work-related stress (WRS) in universities. The rapid changes that academics have experienced over recent years are resulting in several challenges for those who work in higher education institutions (Urbina-Garcia, 2020). Studies across different cultural contexts have shown that rising job demands, both in quantity (e.g., work overload) and quality (e.g., increasing administrative demands), may negatively affect academics' mental health and well-being; in turn, this may lead to excessive WRS, burnout, and mental health issues (Szromek, et al., 2020). Italian universities are required to assess WRS by the Legislative Decree 81/2008 and consequently to take actions to manage it and promote well-being for the academic population. According to the literature and preliminary evidence collected by the QoL@Work network (Brondino et al., 2022) universities involved in the WRS assessment can find it difficult to promote and evaluate interventions on aspects of work and work organization in order to protect employees from psychosocial risks.

In addition, research shows difficulties to translate action plans into practice, by focusing on the impact of barriers and facilitators on the implementation process and outcomes.

The purpose of this study is twofold: collecting updated data on a sample of Italian universities on the diffusion of interventions to promote wellbeing for the academic work population, after assessing the psychosocial risks. In addition, deepening the understanding of key processes and conditions that can facilitate or impede the implementation of interventions and their evaluation in the academic context. In particular we are interested in exploring how universities moved from assessing academic psychosocial risks to designing and implementing interventions.

Design

The study involves two steps. In the first step, one key informant of 21 Italian universities was invited to complete an online survey on the implementation phase of the WRS assessment and management process implemented in his/her university. Questions were about whether a WRS assessment was realized and whether interventions to promote wellbeing were identified, the target population (administrative staff, faculty members and researchers, post-doc researchers and PhD students) and the duration of the process. In the second step a questionnaire will be proposed to participants who identified actions to promote wellbeing in their assessment process. Areas of the investigation are: the design and the implementation of interventions, the type of actions, the monitoring plan and methods, the involvement of workers, the barriers and the facilitators of the whole process.

Results (if applicable)

Preliminary findings of the first survey showed that 18 assessment surveys have been put in place in 12 Universities between 2018 and 2023. In most cases professors and researchers were involved in the assessment (50%), followed by administrative staff (35%). More rarely, the participants were post-doc researchers (20%) or PhD students (15%). The duration of the process varied between 3 and 24 months. Not in all cases interventions were identified, highlighting the possible difficulties in the transition from the assessment phase to the intervention management phase.

The data collection of the second step, focused on the actual implementation of interventions, is in progress.

Implications

The results could have several implications at organizational and systemic levels, since, considering the Italian context, the focus of the national strategy to WRS has been on assessing rather than managing psychosocial risks (Di Tecco et al., 2020). Sharing cross-institutional evidence about recognized good practices to promote wellbeing for the academic population could help organizations in identifying interventions for their context. At the systemic level shedding a light on the diffusion of interventions can sustain a culture for healthy universities at the national and international level. Also the identification of common challenges and key processes that help universities in implementing interventions could offer evidence to better design and manage the implementation stage.

Acknowledgments

Resources

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